

Geochemistry of the Ediacaran–Early Cambrian transition in Central Iberia: tectonic setting and isotope sources

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The geochemistry and Sm-Nd isotope signatures of thick sedimentary series showing a complete Ediacaran–Early Cambrian stratigraphic transition, widely exposed in large Variscan anticlines in the southern part of the Central Iberian Zone (Iberian Massif), have been investigated in order to constrain the tectonic setting of this transition. Two different stratigraphic units appear below the Ordovician series: the Early Cambrian Pusa Shales Formation rests unconformably on fine-grained greywackes of the Late Ediacaran Lower Alcudian Formation. Twelve samples of formation were taken in the Valdelacasa and Central Extremadura anticlines, respectively.

The chemical classification of these shales and greywackes is in good agreement with their characteristic compositional groups. Minor compositional variation of Si, Ti, Al, Fe, Mg and K in shales, which have concentrations close to those of PAAS (Post-Archean Australian Shale), argue against important chemical alteration by post-depositional processes. The relatively high $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and low $\text{K}_2\text{O}/\text{Na}_2\text{O}$ ratios in greywacke samples reflect a predominance of immature sediments, with little evidence of weathering. Both types of samples show little variation in REE content, with fractionation patterns very similar to PAAS, characterized by moderate LREE-enrichment compared to almost-flat HREE patterns. All samples show a slight Eu anomaly. Th/Sc, La/Sc, and Ti/Zr values for shales suggest mixing sources, but Ti/Zr and Zr/Sc values from the greywackes seem to indicate a predominance of felsic sources, confirmed by the low abundances of Cr and Ni.

Trace elements contents in the greywackes indicate deposition of turbidites in a sedimentary basin associated with an active margin (volcanic arc). However, the compositions of the shales are more compatible with a tectonic setting related to passive margins, with Sr, P, and Ti negative anomalies as the most important indicators for such context. ϵNd_{565} values for the Ediacaran greywackes range between -3.0 and -1.4, while ϵNd_{530} in the Cambrian shales ranges from -5.2 to -4.0. TDM ages calculated for both series are Mesoproterozoic ranging 1256–1334 Ma in greywackes and 1444–1657 Ma in shales. According to these data, the Ediacaran–Early Cambrian transition in Central Iberia depicts an evolving tectonic setting in the Gondwanan margin, from active to passive. The Nd model ages are compatible with dominance of a cratonic source, probably the West Africa craton. Younger TDM ages in the Ediacaran greywackes of the Lower Alcudian Formation are compatible with mixed isotopic sources involving juvenile material derived from the volcanic arc. However, the mostly stable context that pertained during Cambrian times favoured the presence of continental isotopic sources, in agreement with the older TDM ages from the Pusa Shale Formation.